

REDUCTION OF DICHROMATE BY IODIDE IN PRESENCE OF CHLORIDES AND BROMIDES

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The reduction of $K_2Cr_2O_7$ by KI in sulphuric acid solutions in presence of varying amounts of chloride and bromide ions has been studied potentiometrically. Presence of small quantities of chloride ions (0.03 M) does not interfere with the normal course of the reaction, the titration curve, showing only one sharp inflexion corresponding to six moles of KI per mole of $K_2Cr_2O_7$. Higher concentrations of chloride ions lead to two inflexions corresponding to three and six moles, the first inflexion indicating the formation of ICl. The final inflexion is quite sharp in 4 N- H_2SO_4 , but not so in smaller concentrations.

Presence of even a small concentration of bromide (0.03 M) affects the reduction process, leading to two inflexions. The final inflexion is still at six moles KI for a rapid titration. In a slow titration there are two inflexions; the first one at three moles KI, followed by the final one, not sharp, at about six moles. The formation of IBr is thus clearly indicated.

Gyani and Prasad (this *Journal*, 1955, **32**, 313) showed that potassium dichromate could be titrated potentiometrically with potassium iodide in hydrochloric and sulphuric acid solutions. Their investigations covered a wide range of acid concentrations. While confirming Hendrixon's results (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, **43**, 1309) that accurate titrations were possible in 2N- H_2SO_4 , they also found that provided sufficient time was allowed for equilibrium, the correct end-point corresponding to

could be obtained with weaker solutions. They found that the reduction of dichromate took place in two well-defined steps in HCl, corresponding to the formation of ICl (3 moles KI) and complete reduction of dichromate (6 moles KI). The reaction in HCl was quicker. It appears therefore that chloride ions may materially affect the reduction of dichromate by KI, and so also may bromide ions. We therefore undertook these potentiometric titrations in H_2SO_4 solutions, chlorides and bromides being present in varying quantities.

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The Reaction between $K_2Cr_2O_7$ and KI in presence of Cl^- .—The experimental procedure has been described previously by Gyani and Prasad (*loc. cit.*). 0.005 M-Dichromate (100 c.c.) usually in 4N- H_2SO_4 was titrated with normal KI in the burette. Varying quantities of chloride were present as noted below.

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|-----------------|-------------------------------|-----------------------------------|
| (A) 0.03 M-NaCl | (C) 0.03 M-NH ₄ Cl | (E) Saturated NaCl |
| (B) 0.03 M-KCl | (D) N-NaCl | (F) Saturated NH ₄ Cl. |

Two more titrations were carried out in presence of saturated NaCl (G) in 2N acid, (H) in normal acid. The corresponding graphs are shown in Fig. 1.

In A, B and C, the mixture became red after the first c. c. of KI added, but in D, E, F and G, the red colour initially produced became pale greenish yellow on shaking till the first inflexion was reached, after which the yellow changed sharply to red. Except in F, iodine was ultimately precipitated. Initial dips were observed in the graph A, B and C, but were not reproducible. They all showed steep inflexions at 6 moles KI per mole $K_2Cr_2O_7$. The graphs D to G show two inflexions: the first at 3 moles and the second at 6 moles KI. The first one in D was only barely perceptible. The second one became less and less steep, passing from E to H (smaller concentrations of H_2SO_4).

FIG. 1

Reaction in presence of Bromide Ions.—These titrations were repeated in presence of bromides: (A) $0.03M$ -KBr + $4N$ - H_2SO_4 , (B) $0.03M$ -KBr + N -acid, (C) M -KBr + $4N$ acid, (D) M -KBr + $2N$ -acid and (E) saturated KBr + $4N$ acid. All the reaction mixtures, except A and B, were kept in glass-stoppered bottles for 24 to 48 hours, before titration. This slight change in procedure was suggested by the quite steep (but not reproducible) initial inflexions in graphs A and B. The results are summarised in Table I; graphs appear in Fig 2.

TABLE I

Graph.	Normality of		Period of storage.	Moles KI/mole $K_2Cr_2O_7$		Remarks
	KBr.	H_2SO_4		1st inf.	2nd inf.	
A	0.03	4.0	Nil	1.0	6.0	
B	0.03	1.0	"	0.5	6.0	
C	1.00	4.0	24 hrs	3.0	6.0	2nd inf. not steep
D	1.00	2.0	"	2.9	6.2	Do
E	Sat.	4.0	48	3.6	7.2	Do

It will be seen that neither the first nor the second inflexion is independent of conditions, the first, being much less so. A decrease in the concentration of H_2SO_4

appears to bring about a decrease in the KI consumed (for the first inflexion) which is increased by increasing KBr concentration. When much bromide is present, the total KI required is more than is necessary for the complete reduction of $K_2Cr_2O_7$.

FIG. 2

The colour of the reaction mixture in A and B at the beginning of the titration had a greenish tinge, whereas in C, D and E, it was dark greenish yellow, indicating a gradual reduction of $Cr_2O_7^{2-}$ to Cr^{3+} . When the first drops of KI were added to A or B, the mixture turned deep red which changed to greenish yellow on shaking. This persisted till the first inflexion appeared when it changed to red and, iodine was precipitated. Addition of KI in C, D and E produced iodine which redissolved, developing a brown colour. This changed to deep reddish brown quite sharply at the first inflexion.

DISCUSSION

Fig. (1) shows that if enough chloride (at least normal) be present, the reduction of $K_2Cr_2O_7$ by KI takes place stepwise, ICl being formed as an intermediate compound. The reactions then are

It has been noted previously by Gyani and Prasad (*loc. cit.*) that $N/2$ -HCl fails to produce the first inflexion, which agrees with the present observations.

A much smaller concentration of bromide can bring about the two-stage reduction of potassium dichromate, a concentration of even 0.03N being enough (Table I). There is nothing against the supposition that bromine is liberated in the first instance

which reacts with KI to furnish IBr, followed by liberation of I₂ with further addition of KI. The reactions may be written as follows:

This mechanism agrees with the suggestion of Britton and Britton concerning reduction of bromine by iodide ions in acid solutions (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 3879). Contrary to their observations, however, we find that the second inflexion is never quite steep and may occur at more than six moles KI per mole dichromate. Reaction (iii) deserves more consideration, and further work is in progress.

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